

OPPORTUNITIES FOR ENGLISH TEACHERS AND THE PROMOTION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE PROMOTION IN UZBEKISTAN

Ibragimova Madina Mamasolievna

Tashkent vocational school №1 specialized for people with disabilities
English Teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7505472>

Annotation: With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the peculiarities of our time, special attention is paid to a new approach to the educational process and its organization, using its potential. The XXI century is the age of high technologies, and our modern youth is not only in the spirit of the times, but also in step with the development of the electronic world.

Key words: educational process, modern profession, democratic state, media, modern - communication technologies.

The noble goals and deep thinking of the President to educate the younger generation, to bring up a new generation with a strong civic position, well-versed in modern professions, intellectually gifted, physically mature, no less than anyone else. The strategy we have adopted is the implementation of such important historical documents as the Law on Education, the National Program for Personnel Training, the State National Program for the Development of School Education. clearly confirmed that.

In his congratulatory message to teachers and coaches of Uzbekistan on the occasion of their professional holiday, the head of our state said: "First of all, all our efforts in this direction would inevitably fail without bringing up a new generation capable of such a great work." Indeed, our lives today show how justified this decision was.

As a result of the use of the Internet and its great potential in foreign language teaching, the prospects for the introduction of multimedia technologies in the educational and pedagogical process are becoming more and more obvious. As you know, the Internet as a main means of communication is divided into four areas:

- Internet as a means of obtaining information;
- Internet as a means of communication;
- Internet as a learning tool;
- The Internet is a means of entertainment.

At the same time, a great deal of attention is paid to training to work with the main means of communication (e-mail, chat) in the search for information on the

network. Initially, the exchange of information is limited to written text, but gradually graphic and audio documents are added.

Several didactic issues can be addressed through the use of ICT and, in particular, the Internet in foreign language classes. Of these, when testing students' knowledge:

- various on-line, ie interactive tests;
- off-line tests, ie the use of electronic versions of tests;
- There are many tests on the Internet for students from elementary to advanced level, such as TOEFL and IELTS.

The advantage of such tests for the student is an objective and quick response. Simultaneous testing of students with different levels of knowledge in explaining a new topic: improving the quality of lessons through photos, clips, movies, videos, for example: students not only get simple information about different foreign countries from the text of the book, but also virtual tours, videos, spoons, clips about the traditions and customs of foreign countries.

It is one of the most effective ways to learn and use a foreign language. You will be able to communicate with foreign speakers through the Internet. Writing exercises can be improved by writing a letter via e-mail. The most important issue is the introduction of modern communication technologies in the educational process, their purposeful and accurate, effective use, through which the student's interest in a foreign language, to increase the effectiveness of teaching. This will allow for the use of innovative educational technologies and increase demand. There are several types of innovative educational technologies available today. When they are used extensively and in a variety of ways to cover a topic in class, the effectiveness of the lesson is high and the interest of the students in the lesson is increased. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education by bringing innovations into the educational process and their implementation.

The use of a variety of role-playing, action games in foreign language teaching increases both interest in the lesson and language learning. By working in pairs or small groups, it helps students communicate with others. The use of graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important visits in the coverage of the topic and its delivery to students. It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to illuminate a topic. When teaching a foreign language, it is advisable to use graphic organizers to explain new words and grammatical rules. These are also easy to remember when given by graphic organizers. The use of different tables in the process of teaching a foreign

language is also very effective. Using tables in the learning process, students can follow a specific grammatical rule, such as composing sentences using tenses and placing new words. At a time when there is a high need for learning a foreign language, the effective use of modern information technologies, innovative educational technologies in the educational process makes this process more effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies lies in their correct and effective use in the educational process.

In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods and games stimulate the student's interest in knowledge. The student tries to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students the subjects of the educational process.

References:

1. Adult ESL Classroom Strategies and Lesson Ideas. Chapter 3. Global Talent Bridge. (2012)
2. Bolshaya Sovetskaya Entsiklopediya. [Large Soviet Encyclopedia]. Moscow, Soviet Encyclopedia. Vol. 20, 1957.
3. Chen Jiamu, 1997. The right methods for adults. On English acquisition/learning. *Análise Psicológica*, 4 (XV).

